

IN THE SEARCH FOR THE FUTURE ENGINEER: THE EELISA DISCIPLINARY BROADENING WORKSHOP EXPERIENCE

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ABSTRACT

The emerging adhocacy of sustainability in every field of life, do also claims its legacy in the field of education, particularly in the discipline of engineering. Institutions necessitate to adapt their curriculums to the possible changes so that the engineers of the future are ready to address interdisciplinary and evolving challenges in their careers. As a European University Alliance aiming to define and implement a European engineering model, EELISA project has a dedicated work package to explore and propose various approaches to address this challenge by deploying disciplinary broadening workshops. This paper scrutinizes the initial outputs of the first full-day workshop organized by three partner universities of the alliance under

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the theme of “Cities and Communities” in October 2021, and opens it to a broader discussion.

This paper is structured in four parts while deploying qualitative research methods to analyze the collected data. Initially, it expresses the role of EELISA University, the state-of-the-art skills of today’s engineers and the challenges for enriching them to materialize the vision of European engineering, including bridging and expanding disciplinary domains. The second part explains the workshop structure that was organized under four interdisciplinary subtopics related to the theme to increase the involvement of various engineering and non-engineering academics and professionals. Then the workshop outputs, the participants’ brainstorming about the skills, competences, proposals to overcome challenges and barriers are conveyed. The final part summarizes the workshop results and introduces valuable inputs to the search for the European engineer profile and the roadmap of the EELISA.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 EELISA European University

The **European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance (EELISA)** is the first alliance of Higher Education Institutions from different countries in Europe meant to define and implement a **common model of *European engineer*** rooted in society. The alliance of nine universities from seven countries has a mission to transform European higher education into the seed for a future in which society masters global challenges with smart and sustainable solutions enabled by engineering. EELISA envisions a higher education system that enables student citizenship participation and employability by:

- *Evolving interdisciplinary engineering learning*
- *Fostering knowledge and technology transfer*
- *Stimulating inclusiveness and diversity*
- *Connecting academic excellence to social impact and commitment*

The EELISA project has nine work packages to realize the mission and vision of the project ranging from curriculum development to education management and accreditation, from establishing communities for societal challenges to the link between Education, Research and Innovation, from effective internships to mobility with inclusive student participation.

1.2 Disciplinary Broadening Work Package

EELISA project has a dedicated work package called “Disciplinary Broadening” (WP8) with an ultimate goal of enriching the skills of the engineers of the future after an exchange with other disciplines and reciprocally incorporating engineering methods in other areas by realizing tasks of

- Identifying interdisciplinary needs of the engineer of the future
- Designing of bridging models for multiskilling in engineering education
- Identifying engineering skills needs of other professional domains
- Designing bridging models between engineering skills and other professional domains
- Implementing multiskilling pilots for other disciplinary domains
- Gathering feedback and adapting pilots

The objective of the work package is to nurture international and interdisciplinary stakeholders of academic and non-academic members of our communities, who address complex problems. EELISA’s vision of European Engineering will help us bridge and expand disciplinary domains, and focus on skills needed by engineers as well as engineering skills needed by other professional fields.

1.3 Disciplinary Broadening Workshops

The main activity of the Disciplinary Broadening Work Package of the EELISA Project is a series of full-day workshops. These workshops are designed to help EELISA meet the specific goals of the work package by starting with the description

of skills of the engineer of the future in various disciplines and exploring ways of enriching engineering skills with non-engineering competences and introducing engineering skills to other professional domains. Workshops help collect inputs from the stakeholders with various profiles including academics, higher education administrators, student representatives, representatives of scientific societies, industry/society stakeholders and policymakers, and representatives of placement offices.

Outcomes of the disciplinary broadening workshops will provide direct input into the effort of defining the European Engineer Profile led by WP2 of the EELISA project. This effort is not limited to workshops but also utilizes interviews with top professionals in Europe, surveys with various stakeholders, and the literature. Identification of professional skills is not a brand new point of interest.

European Society of Engineering Education has a dedicated Special Interest Group on “Engineering Skills”, where Murphy et al. emphasize the importance of the regional variations in the definitions while elaborating on common issues within the formation and education of the engineer [1]. A-STEP 2030 project underlines the importance of skills for engineers to address challenges associated with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) [2], which are in line with two pilot tracks of the EELISA project, **Smart, Green and Resilient Cities** and **Sustainable and Smart Industry**. Crean et al. obtained similar needs in particular for the concepts of society and sustainability as part of a study on mapping the development of professional skills in a structural engineering program [3]. The interdisciplinary approach is another aspect that came out of the study by Flament and Kövesi especially to address the addressing sustainability issues [4]. Beagon et al. [5] identified sustainability competences from the perspectives of students, industry and academics in four European countries. Their findings are mostly in line with the findings of the European [6] and International [7] framework competences. Disciplinary broadening workshops have the potential to contribute to the literature.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Cities and Communities Workshop

The theme of the first workshop was “Cities and Communities”, which took place online on October 26th, 2021. Including three faculty members from the host institution, the organizing team of the workshop consists of eight professors from three EELISA partner institutions.

The flow of the full-day event contains two keynote speakers in the morning and afternoon sessions, a single panel discussion after the keynote in the morning, parallel interactive workshop sessions managed on a Miro board before the noon and after the second keynote in the afternoon, and a closing discussion session for the organizing team to wrap up the outcomes of the workshop.

2.2 Parallel Workshop Sessions

Four subtopics of the Cities and Communities Workshop include “**Infrastructure and Mobility**”, “**Energy and Climate Change**”, “**Culture and Inclusiveness**” and “**Buildings**”, which are discussed in four breakout rooms, BR1, BR2, BR3, BR4, respectively. In each track of focus, the workshop coordinators accordingly aimed to attain participants’ responses on four interconnected inquiries that constitute the essences of the disciplinary broadening attempts: *mapping the skill gaps, mapping the disciplinary boundaries and learning* in the morning session; and *proposing innovative teaching and learning activities*, and proposing the *bridging models* in the afternoon session (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. High-level preview of the miro board designed for the workshop.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Workshop Participant Profile

Among 64 registrants, 44 attended the event, 30 of which were female. The participant profile was predominantly from academia including faculty members, Ph.D. students, and staff. During the discussions in the breakout rooms, some of the participants from academia shared their work experiences or collaborations with partners from public bodies, industry or NGOs. In addition to that, the keynote speakers’ profile and speeches during the event indicate ties and interactions with various stakeholders.

- Roger Hadgraft (Keynote Speaker 1): “Educating Interdisciplinary Engineers for Future Cities and Communities”

- Overview of a recent review of engineering education in Australia conducted by the Australian Council of Engineering Deans and some examples of curriculum changes to achieve these outcomes.
- Hatice Sözer: “Preparing students to the professional life”
 - Interdisciplinary project-based educational program, InterPROfessional Projects Program at the Illinois Institute of Technology at Chicago, to prepare students for a dynamic and competitive global environment.
- Gülcemal Alhanlıoğlu: “A method proposal for gaining practical practices in higher education”
 - Practice of working together with other disciplines by trainings to introduce business life and laws & regulations, economic knowledge and practice of working together with other disciplines.
- Bettina Szimonetta Jäger: “My journey into the world of complexity”
 - Interdisciplinary work experience at the municipality and collaboration opportunities between the university education and the local government from the perspective of a doctoral student with a non-engineering background.
- Paolo Dario: “The RoboTown vision: bridging research and innovation, education and societal impact”
 - The interaction between local entities and disciplines to integrate robotics into living environments and cities.
- Zeynep Erden Bayazit: “Spanning Boundaries in Education: Fire-Up Changemaker Community Experience”
 - Overview of relevant interdisciplinary, interinstitutional and intersectoral challenge-based innovation activities supported by a partner entrepreneurship and innovation centre.
- Birgül Tantekin Ersolmaz (Keynote Speaker 2): “Opportunities, Challenges and Good Practices in the Accreditation of Interdisciplinary Programs”
 - Main features of outcome-based accreditation and discuss the opportunities and challenges for accreditation of interdisciplinary programs.

3.2 Workshop Results

About the initial inquiry on mapping the skill gaps, most of the participants in each sub-track reflected their responses based on hard and soft skills. These skills were reflected either as the missing qualities, or the ones that were obliged to be attained from diverse disciplinary backgrounds of engineering and non-engineering groups.

When the outcomes are categorized in similar groups, the urgencies for enhancing the **trans-disciplinary knowledge skills, system thinking, assessment skills, robotic skills**, and other related skills on **control and automation**, skills

for **sustainability** as well as **business and management** appeared as the emerging **hard skills** for the disciplinary broadening (Table 1).

Table 1. Thematic categorization of hard skills for disciplinary broadening in breakout rooms

Trans-disciplinary knowledge production	Social sciences skills for the engineering (BR3)
	Social science skills for non-engineers (BR4)
	Health science skills for non-engineers (BR4)
	Psychology skills for non-engineers (BR4)
	Analytical skills for non-engineers (BR2) (BR3)
	Indigenous knowledge (BR3)
	Science knowledge (BR1)
	Lack of the knowledge regarding the strategic and legal context (BR2)
	Analytical skills for non-engineers (BR3)
	Thermodynamics (BR1)
	Utilities (thermal, electrical, etc.) (BR1)
System thinking	Systems thinking, relating concepts (BR1)
	Ability to understand indirect and direct impacts (BR2)
	Problem identification and definition and redefinition- for engineers (BR4)
	Synthesis of different type of data (BR2)
Assessment skills	Awareness capabilities (BR1)
	Vulnerability assessment (BR2)
	Adaptation-oriented evaluation (BR2)
	Professionals: research methodologies and perspectives from STS (BR4)
Robotics, control and automation	Robotic skills for non-engineering background (BR3)
	ICT skills for non/engineering professionals (BR3)
	Infrastructure and building informatics, communication systems(BR1)
	Energy storage technologies (batteries, thermal storage, etc.) (BR1)
Green skills	Sustainable energy technologies (BR1)
	Green financial tools (BR2)
	Sustainability management skills (BR2)

	Socio-economic aspects of climate studies (BR2)
	Ecology and sustainability management skills (BR3)
	Misinterpretation of the relationship among sustainability and climate adaptation (BR2)
Business and management skills	Business administration and entrepreneurship skills (BR3)
	Business administration / entrepreneurship skills will be needed for successful implementation of ideas (BR3)
	Audience analysis and management tool (BR3)
	Change and innovation management skills (BR3)

On the other side, related with the **soft skills** we observed a broader variability of issues being reflected in each sub-track. When the outcomes were categorized accordingly, the urgencies of **communication skills**, skills for **resilience**, **inclusiveness in multi-levels**, **collaboration**, **multi-disciplinary** and **system thinking** as well as **creative thinking skills** appeared as the emerging skills for the disciplinary broadening (Table 2).

Table 2. Thematic categorization of soft skills for disciplinary broadening in breakout rooms

Communication (conflict resolution-knowledge skills)	Communication (BR4)
	Social skills (BR1)
	Language skills (BR1)
	Psychological skills (BR2)
	Relationship with friendly and flexibility (BR3)
	Professionals: conflict resolution (BR4)
Resilience	Dealing with uncertainty (BR4)
Multi-level of inclusiveness	Human centered approach (BR3)
	Take care for disadvantages groups (BR3)
	Thinking with ngo and also global and local problems (BR3)
	Awareness capabilities (environmental and social awareness) (BR1)
	Environmental and social awareness (BR4)
	Dealing with real world limitations (designers) (BR4)
	Problem defining and re-defining (BR4)
	Collaboration culture (BR1)

Collaborative skills	Collaboration skills with engineers and design studios (BR3)
	Empathy and problem solving skills (BR3)
	Teamwork (BR1) (BR3)
	Time-management (BR1)
	Sense of responsibility (BR1)
Relating concepts and applying them to multidisciplinary projects, systems thinking	Working in multidisciplinary teams (BR1)
	Introducing multidisciplinary projects at first courses (BR1)
	Industrial exposure (BR1)
	Lacking knowledge in social areas (BR1)
Creativity, curiosity	Re-assigning the notion of complexity in non-engineering background (BR3)
	Thinking outside the box (BR4)

Briefly, in this initial inquiry about required skills for disciplinary broadening, immediate hard skills for enhancing interdisciplinary and trans-disciplinary knowledge such as management and robotic skills and advanced knowledge on sustainability were proposed while blending them with advanced knowledge of humanities and social sciences. Besides, analytical and qualitative assessment skills have been addressed throughout the breakout rooms. In addition, advanced communication skills, problem finding and solving skills, system and complex thinking skills and creative thinking skills further emerged as soft skills that are required for advanced disciplinary broadening.

About the initial inquiry on the ***mapping the disciplinary boundaries and learning***, most of the participants in each sub-track developed their responses based on hard and soft skills that are required and to be attained from both disciplinary backgrounds of engineering and non-engineering.

So, during the parallel discussions in the breakout rooms, inquiries related with the *tertiary or higher education culture, curriculum, teaching strategies and methods, institutional challenges, global challenges, bureaucratic structures, funding opportunities and sectoral linkages* emerged as the forthcoming issues, that can be further detailed into further permutations with each other.

About the initial inquiry on the ***proposing innovative teaching and learning activities***, most of the participants in each sub-track developed their responses on the basis of hard and soft skills that are required and to be attained from both disciplinary backgrounds of engineering and non-engineering.

When the inquiries are examined in detail, recommendations about **curriculum improvements** are visible on behalf of enhancing the content of courses in terms of interdisciplinary and trans-disciplinary broadening of knowledge while **updating them in relation to global challenges such as sustainability**. Beyond content, **educational operations** such as student numbers capacities, teaching capacities, international collaborations and extracurricular activities, are also highlighted in the discussions.

Based on the synthesis of the workshop content by the rapporteur and organizing team, a number of operational statements have been identified including **interdisciplinary degrees, graduation design projects and courses, credited interdisciplinary activities, industry-sponsored internships, industry-sponsored courses, industrial design department project courses, eelisa-wide courses, integrated engineering programs, interdepartmental student activities outside the classroom, mobility for innovative teaching/learning activities, experience-based activities, conference participation, competition activities, center of excellence in engineering education and center of excellence in mobility and infrastructure**. Supporting information for these operational statements included the target students, learning outcomes, teaching forms, required infrastructure, and involved academic sectors for guidance.

Workshop results constitute relevant information for various work packages of EELISA. Some of these are direct inputs to various work packages and tasks, while other work packages may find them useful. For instance, the skills explored during the workshop are potential inputs for the task of proposing a shared definition of the profile of the European Engineer by WP2. The innovative learning and teaching activities, and bridging models proposed during the workshop are direct candidates for the design and implementation of WP8 multiskilling pilot applications in engineering education, which will be managed in coordination with the WP2.

Other indirect relevant information from the disciplinary workshop series may help WP3 representatives to reassess and update the curriculum for contemporary teaching inquiries and paradigms, diminishing workload; to inspire many different learning activities such as solar decathlon, by communities developed by WP4; to guide implementing institutional collaborations via diverse teaching methods of small project competitions, vertical studios, joint research studios, international training opportunities, exchange of qualified researchers and graduate students organized by WP5; to guide establishing sectoral collaboration in the research facilities, sectoral needs and knowledge integration to the curriculums, enhancing institutional budgets by WP6; to enhancing students engagement to real-world problems, problem finding activities for students, providing connections with different stakeholders and NGOs, extensive inclusiveness in developing innovative curricular and extra-curricular activities by WP7; to urge organizing relevant events; meetings, workshops, seminars, decathlons, online dissemination such as newsletters, open-source digital archive of events by WP9.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The first disciplinary broadening workshop of the EELISA project provided a brainstorming opportunity for the partners of the European University Alliance partners to initiate the search for the interdisciplinary skills of the European Engineer of the future under the theme of “Cities and Communities”. The theme presents a perfect match with two pilot tracks of EELISA project and Sustainable Development Goals. Workshop results underline the skill gaps of today’s engineers, the barriers as well as the need for exchange between the engineering and non-engineering professionals. Potential proposals started to pile up for potential multiskilling pilots to be designed and implemented as part of the EELISA project.

EELISA’s second disciplinary broadening workshop in 2021 was on “Sensing Sciences and Technologies”. There are at least five workshops in progress in the year 2022. The themes of them include but are not limited to the following : “Architecture and Archeology”, “Digital Philology”, “Teaching Sustainable Development”, “Data Science for Industries” and “Managing Cities”.

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